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MUNDARIJA

Ta'lim jarayonini transformatsiya qilishning samarali yo'llari.....	10
Mirzayeva Faroxat Odiljonovna	
Maktab darsliklari innovatsion o'qitish vositasi sifatida.....	14
Abdullayeva Maftuna Odiljon qizi	
O'quvchilarda raqamli kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning samarali usullari.....	18
Aliyeva Shahrizoda Berdimurod qizi	
Fizikada darsdan tashqari to'garak mashg'ulotlarida (7-sinf) o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirish	20
Allayarova Sayyora Xadjibayevna	
Kouching texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarining amaliy kompetentligini rivojlantirish.....	26
Axmedova Sarvinoz Azatovna	
Pedagogik ta'limda klaster metodlarining dunyo mamlakatlari tajribasidagi o'rni.....	29
Badalov Dilmurod Abdixalilovich	
Human-AI Collaboration in Teaching: a New Paradigm in Pedagogy	32
Baxarova Asila Shermatovna	
Orienting 7th-Grade Students Towards Career Choices Through Interdisciplinary Teaching of Physics	35
Boyturayeva Gulbahor Kamoliddin qizi, Zakhidov Ibrokhimjon Obidjonovich	
Muhandislik sohasi ta'lim yo'nalishi bo'yicha tadbirkorlik g'oyasini shakllantirish usullari	41
Butayev Tuxtasin	
Chet tillarini o'rganishda eraklarning roli va ahamiyati	46
Djuraeva Gavxar Normurotovna	
Ta'limda "boshqaruv", "kompetentlik" hamda "boshqaruv kompetentligi" tushunchalari.....	49
Egamberdiyeva Gulxayohon Bahodir qizi	
Grammar in Spoken and Written Communication: Practical Aspects – the Use of Communication and Common Errors in Grammar Usage	53
Elmirzayeva Maftuna Dasmurod kizi, Mustafoyeva Nigina Shuhrat qizi	
Gadjetlar bolaning rivojlanishi va sog'lig'iga qanday ta'sir qiladi	57
Fayziyeva Nodira Sobirovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining konstruksiyalash va modellashtirish kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish.....	61
Haydarov Mirjalol Shog'dorovich	
Innovatsion yondashuv asosida "Qon aylanish sistemasi" mavzusi bo'yicha nazariy mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish va o'tkazish metodikasi (8-sinf misolida).....	64
Ibragimova Kamola Zokirjon qizi	
"Bolalar folklori" fanini o'qitishda talabalar tadqiqotchilik kompetensiyasini akmeologik yondashuv asosida takomillashtirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	68
Ilxamova Bibinur Po'latjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida iqtidorli bolalar bilan ishlash texnologiyalari	71
Karimjonova Dilrabo Akbarali qizi	
Gamification in Primary School: How Game-Based Methods Increase Motivation to Learn.....	74
Khaitova Nazokat	
Enhancing Project Competencies in Academic English: Integrating Music, Drama, and Technology in Engineering Education.....	78
Abdullayeva Komila Timurovna	
Maktabgacha ta'limda inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishning dolzarb masalalari.....	81
Mamatisayeva Surayyo Axmadjon qizi	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarining boshlang'ich sinflarida "Lesson study" metodikasidan foydalanish.....	87
Muradova Feruza Abdurazak qizi	
Ta'limni raqamlashtirish sharoitida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetensiyasini shakllantirish – ijtimoiy-pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	90
Musaeva Umida Xolmatjonovna	

Zamonaviy ta'limga asoslangan maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarining didaktik salohiyatini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	94
O'rinova Feruza O'ljayevna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kommunikativ ko'nikmalar – ijtimoiy-psixologik fenomen sifatida	98
Otabek Abduraxmonov	
The Development of Technical University Students' Skills for Creative Engineering Projects	102
Parmankulov Farkhod Nurali ugli	
Ijodkorlik asosida bo'lajak tarbiyachilar kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirish	110
Quysinova Shahlo Nasim qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quv jarayonini loyihalashtirishda innovatsion yondashuv	114
Rahmonov Azamat Ruzvonovich	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning integrativ yondashuv asosida kreativ qobiliyatini shakllantirish	117
Riskitillayeva Nihola Abduvohid qizi	
Kasbiy rivojlanishning umumiy konsepsiyasi va uning ta'lim jarayonidagi ahamiyati.....	120
Turg'unov Axror Yodgor o'g'li	
Ona tili ta'limida fonetik va orfografik mashqlar tasnifi.....	124
Urazboyeva Sabohat Ortiqboyevna	
Shaxs oti yasovchi -chi affksining faollashuvi	128
Usmanov Abdijabbar Norbo'tayevich	
Experimental Study of Developing Students' Inclusive Readiness in Higher Education Pedagogy Based on a Competency Approach.....	131
Xafizova Umida Juraboy qizi	
Texnik sohalar bo'yicha ingliz tilidagi terminologiyani o'rgatish metodikasi	134
Xolxodjayeva Dilfuza Shoakrom qizi	
Biologiya o'quv fanidan olimpiadalar tashkil etishning pedagogik shart- sharoitlari	139
Zayniyev Suxrobjon Islombek o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim tarixiy paradigmalarining shakllanishi va ularning rivojlanish bosqichlari.....	143
Ziyoyeva Irodaxon Umidjon qizi	
Теоретические основы профессиональной рефлексии в педагогической деятельности.....	147
Мухсиева А. Ш., Исохонова А. Ш.	
Анализ основных проблем начального образования в контексте современных вызовов.....	150
Латипова Маърифат Салохиддиновна	
Pedagogik faoliyatda praksiologiyaning o'rni.....	155
Kaldibekova Anargul Sotbarovna, Rahmonova Sevara Burxon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida multimedia texnologiyasidan foydalanish uslubiyoti.....	158
Ashurova Dilduza Nabiyevna, Shokirova Durdona Shuxrat qizi, Toshtemirova Kamola Ergashevna	

ORIENTING 7TH-GRADE STUDENTS TOWARDS CAREER CHOICES THROUGH INTERDISCIPLINARY TEACHING OF PHYSICS

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of guiding school students toward careers that match their talents and interests, introducing them to modern professions, and ensuring that the knowledge acquired through general education contributes to their future professional preparation. One of the effective teaching methods that facilitates this process is interdisciplinary teaching, in which topics studied in different subjects reinforce students' understanding and help them recognize their innate abilities.

The study highlights that students' ability to generate new ideas, think independently, and solve problems effectively is directly linked to the depth of their knowledge. In this regard, an interdisciplinary approach in physics lessons plays a crucial role. The article presents a table demonstrating the correlation between physics topics in the 7th grade and various professions, as well as the connections between demonstrations, laboratory work, practical exercises, and different career fields.

It emphasizes that the effective use of interdisciplinary connections allows students to explore practical applications of physical phenomena and laws, approaching them creatively when necessary. Additionally, it notes that while school students often struggle to substantiate their career choices comprehensively, most strive to make conscious decisions. Well-organized interdisciplinary lessons can help nurture their interests and provide meaningful career guidance.

Key words: student, modern professions, motion, knowledge, career guidance, physics teaching, interest, interdisciplinary connection, effective utilization, production.

Аннотация: Ushbu maqolada maktab o'quvchilarini o'z iste'dodlari va qiziqishlariga mos kasblarni tanlashga yo'naltirish, ularni zamonaviy kasblar bilan tanishtirish hamda umumiy ta'lim jarayonida egallagan bilimlarining kelajakdagi kasbiy tayyorgarligiga hissa qo'shishini ta'minlash masalasi muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu jarayonni samarali amalga oshiruvchi ta'lim usullaridan biri fanlararo ta'lim bo'lib, bunda turli fanlarda o'rganiladigan mavzular o'quvchilarning bilimlarini mustahkamlaydi va o'zlaridagi tug'ma qobiliyatlarini anglashlariga yordam beradi.

Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'quvchilarning yangi g'oyalar ishlab chiqarish, mustaqil fikrlash va muammolarni samarali yechish qobiliyatlari bevosita ularning bilimlar chuqurligiga bog'liq. Shu nuqtayi nazardan fizika darslarida fanlararo yondashuv muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada 7-sinf fizika mavzularining turli kasblar bilan o'zaro bog'liqligini ko'rsatuvchi jadval hamda demonstratsiya, laboratoriya ishlari va amaliy mashg'ulotlarning turli kasbiy yo'nalishlar bilan aloqasi keltirilgan.

Fanlararo aloqalardan samarali foydalanish o'quvchilarga fizik hodisa va qonunlarning amaliy qo'llanilishini o'rganishga va zarur hollarda ularga ijodiy yondashishga imkon yaratishi ta'kidlanadi. Shuningdek, maktab o'quvchilari ko'pincha kasb tanlashlarini to'liq asoslashda qiynalsalar-da, ularning aksariyati ongli qaror qabul qilishga intilayotgani qayd etiladi. Yaxshi tashkil etilgan fanlararo darslar o'quvchilarning qiziqishlarini rivojlantirish va sifatli kasbga yo'naltirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quvchi, zamonaviy kasblar, harakat, bilim, kasbga yo'naltirish, fizika o'qitish, qiziqish, fanlararo aloqa, samarali foydalanish, ishlab chiqarish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается важность ориентирования школьников на выбор профессий, соответствующих их талантам и интересам, ознакомления их с современными специальностями, а также обеспечения того, чтобы знания, полученные в ходе общего образования, способствовали их будущей профессиональной подготовке. Одним из эффективных методов обучения, способствующих этому процессу, является межпредметное обучение, при котором темы, изучаемые по разным предметам, усиливают понимание учащимися учебного материала и помогают им раскрыть свои врождённые способности.

Исследование подчёркивает, что способность учащихся генерировать новые идеи, мыслить самостоятельно и эффективно решать проблемы напрямую связана с глубиной их знаний. В этой связи межпредметный подход на уроках физики играет ключевую роль. В статье представлена таблица, демонстрирующая взаимосвязь тем по физике в 7-м классе с различными профессиями, а также связь демонстраций, лабораторных работ и практических упражнений с различными профессиональными направлениями.

Подчёркивается, что эффективное использование межпредметных связей позволяет учащимся исследовать практическое применение физических явлений и законов, а при необходимости подходить к ним творчески. Также отмечается, что школьники зачастую испытывают затруднения с полным обоснованием своего профессионального выбора, однако большинство стремится принимать осознанные решения. Хорошо организованные межпредметные уроки способны способствовать развитию их интересов и оказывать качественную профориентацию.

Ключевые слова: учащийся, современные профессии, движение, знания, профориентация, преподавание физики, интерес, межпредметная связь, эффективное использование, производство.

INTRODUCTION

One of the primary challenges in today's school environment is identifying students' career inclinations upon graduating from secondary school. Career guidance for students can largely be addressed within the school setting. Vocational preparation is an integral component of the continuous education system, fulfilling students' professional training needs and ensuring the formation of personnel equipped with basic professional knowledge and skills for various sectors of the national economy ^[1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

In our country, school psychologists play a key role in studying students' career inclinations and guiding them toward suitable professions. Their responsibilities include: conducting interactive surveys among 7th-grade students to identify their career interests and creating a database based on this information; developing qualification requirements and other educational-methodological documents related to vocational training; coordinating and methodologically supporting vocational education, including designing, approving, and implementing curricula and educational programs.

Additionally, directing students toward professions matching their talents and interests, introducing them to modern careers, and involving 7th–11th-grade students in vocational clubs remain pressing issues ^[2].

The main tasks of career guidance are as follows:

- **Providing career information:** Introducing students to different types of modern industries and the labor market, familiarizing them with the requirements of various professions, and establishing a foundation for providing information about vocational education institutions.

- **Career counseling:** Developing a professional counseling system based on students' interests, inclinations, innate abilities, skills, family environment, regional conditions, and the expectations of students and their parents; offering expert career guidance according to professional requirements.
- **Career diagnosis:** Assessing students' individual psychological and physiological characteristics, age, knowledge levels, skills, and competencies; making final career assessments (diagnostic materials remain confidential and are discussed only with the student and their parents); evaluating students' professional inclinations and personal orientation.
- **Career orientation:** Developing an activity system based on psychological, psycho-physiological, and medical diagnostic results to align students with suitable career paths.

Education, by its nature, is divided into general and specialized types. General secondary education is designed to support personal development and provide students with fundamental knowledge necessary for organizing their life activities.

The knowledge acquired through general education serves as a foundation for specialized education, which focuses on theoretical training and developing practical skills in specific professional fields ^[3]. General secondary education schools introduce the physics curriculum from the 7th grade, and since career guidance efforts also begin at this stage, physics lessons play a crucial role in shaping students' career inclinations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

From the above, it is evident that most career guidance activities align with the educational process. This means that the activities conducted within the teaching and educational processes, as well as the methods, tools, and forms of organizing lessons by teachers, play a crucial role. One such method is interdisciplinary teaching, which enables students to effectively absorb knowledge and realize their innate abilities by integrating topics and concepts learned in different subjects. In turn, this helps students assess their own potential and, most importantly, plan their future careers correctly.

Wilfredo Regueiferos Gutierrez, a researcher at the Cuba Municipal University Center, along with Yaysmara Maritza Madina and Elieser Briso Gonsales, teachers at the Cuban IPU Elvira Cape Lombard Secondary School, discuss this issue in their article "The Interdisciplinarity in the Technical Education and Professional as from the Professionalization of the Contents" ^[5]. They cite several authors, such as Fernando Perera (2000), Delfino Ferreyra (2006), and Peres Ganfong (2006), who have explored technical and vocational education and emphasized the importance of interdisciplinary connections in this field. They highlight the relationship between general education subjects and secondary technical training, stating that the interdisciplinary approach between general and technical subjects is one of the methods that prepares students to take career-oriented actions from the early years of their education, ultimately serving the goal of professionalization.

According to American psychologist Howard Gardner ^[6], regarding interdisciplinary teaching and career guidance, "...human learning abilities vary, and the education system should not be confined to a single standard method." He supports the application of interdisciplinary education in career guidance and argues that students should be provided with opportunities to experiment with different subjects to develop in a direction that matches their interests and abilities. This, in turn, helps cultivate adaptable and innovative professionals for future careers. Gardner has thoroughly substantiated this theory with solid reasoning.

In general, both global and domestic scholars have analyzed the interdisciplinary connections of physics in various aspects and substantiated its effectiveness in education through their research. This demonstrates that organizing and conducting physics lessons within an interdisciplinary framework not only enhances lesson effectiveness but also plays a significant role in shaping students' future career paths.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Any professional activity manifests itself in real conditions, in various ways, and in different forms. Since every action is directed toward a specific object or subject, activity is perceived as a set of object-related actions. For example, the object-related action of a student taking notes during a lesson is focused on writing, which, by making changes in the quantity and quality of the notes in their notebook, enriches their knowledge base. Depending on what professional activity and its constituent object-related actions are directed toward, professional activity is primarily classified into external and internal types.

External professional activity refers to actions aimed at altering the surrounding environment, objects, and phenomena. Internal professional activity, on the other hand, is primarily a cognitive activity derived from the course of pure professional psychological processes. From the perspective of origin, internal cognitive and psychological professional activity begins with external object-related activity. Initially, external object-related activity takes place, and as experience accumulates, these actions gradually transform into internal cognitive

processes. In any situation, all actions are controlled by consciousness from both internal psychological and external coordination perspectives. If you observe a thinking person attentively, you will notice that, although their dominant professional activity is cognitive, their forehead, eyes, and even hand movements can indicate whether they are struggling to reach a conclusion on a complex idea or experiencing satisfaction from discovering a new thought^[3].

A student's knowledge plays a crucial role in generating new ideas. The more knowledge they possess, the easier it is for them to think independently and find solutions to problems. In this process, the knowledge acquired through interdisciplinary lessons is of great importance. For example, it is necessary to indicate professions related to the topics of the 7th grade physics curriculum^[4]. Below, we propose the following examples (Table 1).

Table 1: The relationship between lesson topics and existing professions

Lesson Topic	Relevant Professions	Essential Physics Knowledge for the Specialist
7th Grade		
Pressure in a Static Liquid	Underwater Rescuers	Static liquid pressure, pressure at a certain height
Atmospheric Pressure	Hydrometeorologists, Doctors	Atmospheric pressure, human arterial blood pressure, air humidity
Pressure in Liquids and Gases. Hydraulic Press	Stamping Machine Mechanics, Gas Welders	Pressure in liquids and gases, pressure in solids, manifestation of pressure, transmission of pressure through different materials
Interaction of Objects. Force	Drivers, Mechanics, Athletes, Bakers	Laws of motion, interaction of objects, force units and measuring instruments
Mechanical Power and Its Unit	Drivers, Automotive Technicians	Power, unit of power, horsepower
Light Phenomena. Lens, Magnifying Glass	Engineers, Doctors	Reflection and refraction of light, types of lenses

Elements of career guidance can be integrated into the process of explaining new material, questioning, practical work, and exercises that have an applied component. To effectively address career guidance issues, physics teachers should include the following points in their calendar-thematic plans: introducing students to professions while presenting educational material; studying and developing students' interests, inclinations, and abilities during classroom teaching; assisting students in identifying their interests in specific fields during laboratory and practical activities.

The plan for introducing students to various professions while covering subject topics is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The interrelation of 7th grade physics topics, Demonstrations, Laboratory, and Practical work with existing professions

Topic	Demonstrations, Laboratory, and Practical Work	Industrial Processes and Professions
The Role of Central Asian Scientists in the History of Physics Development	Videos and slides on the application of physics in technology	The importance of mastering the fundamentals of science (physics knowledge) for professional training and skill acquisition
Thermal Phenomena	Expansion of objects when heated. Studying thermal conductivity. Observing heat exchange when mixing water of different temperatures	Locksmiths (boilermakers, knife makers, etc.), craftsmen making blown glass products
Motion and Forces	Laboratory work: Measuring the density of objects of different shapes	Salesperson, Laboratory assistant
Liquid and Gas Pressure	Demonstrating atmospheric pressure in practice	Laboratory assistant for mechanical testing, Engineer at compressor and pump stations, Hydrometeorology specialist
Work and Power. Energy	Studying the working process of various mechanisms (lever, crane, automobiles, etc.)	Drivers, Operators of moving and stationary cranes, Automotive service technicians
Electricity	Measuring current and voltage in an electric circuit. Adjusting current using a rheostat. Studying Ohm's Law	Electricians, Rescue workers

In teaching physics, vocational orientation should neither be separated from studying the topic fundamentals nor disrupt the systematic delivery of knowledge or become merely a routine addition to the presented material.

Additionally, it is recommended to ensure the relevance of studied industrial material by linking it to modern trends, development prospects of relevant sectors of the national economy, and the demand for specialists in local production. It is equally important to establish interdisciplinary polytechnic connections, address problems related to production structure, and highlight the significance of acquired physical knowledge for specific professions in physics-mathematics, industrial technology, or natural sciences.

Furthermore, it is essential to demonstrate extensively the application of studied substances, materials, physical processes, and methods of physical control in various modern production sectors; identify the application of physical laws and theories in technology; develop students' abilities to practically apply acquired knowledge; and foster their independent acquisition of new knowledge regarding the use of physics in diverse professions.

To ensure students are well-prepared for independent professional activities within the education system and make informed career choices aligned with their abilities, schoolteachers must possess high pedagogical skills, deep subject knowledge, and strong didactic abilities. Additionally, linking fundamental subject matter to real-life applications and effectively integrating interdisciplinary connections during lessons is crucial. This stems from the understanding that knowledge acquired by students serves as a foundation for career decision-making.

Prominent Central Asian scholars (Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Ahmad al-Fergani, and others) conducted research in natural sciences, astronomy, mathematics, and philosophy, leaving behind a rich scientific legacy^[4]. For instance, among the great encyclopedic scholars who significantly contributed to the development of physics, Abu Nasr al-Farabi possessed profound knowledge in physics, chemistry, medicine, and biology, establishing connections between these disciplines. Consequently, his research findings have been preserved and handed down through generations.

It should be noted that school students often struggle to fully justify their career choices, although many attempt to approach this issue consciously. Teachers should not only have a deep understanding of theoretical subject content but also systematically present practical aspects of their disciplines, reflecting real-life problems students may encounter in future professional activities.

The content of career guidance for students is shaped by the necessity to cultivate their interests, abilities, understanding of their societal role, and decision-making skills in career selection. For middle-school students, defining their position in life and preparing for it serves as a motivating factor, helping them explore their potential and make informed career choices. During this stage, their socio-psychological competencies develop alongside self-awareness, awareness of their societal position, and attitudes towards their surroundings and the broader world.

Teachers of general education subjects must provide students with comprehensive knowledge that enables them to independently solve problems or difficulties they might encounter, considering their interests, abilities, and aspirations.

Just as it is impossible to forcibly direct textbook topics toward practical applications, students' career inclinations cannot be dictated. Selecting fundamental physical concepts, phenomena, and laws with broad applications in production and human activities logically and systematically requires teachers not only to possess deep theoretical understanding but also to effectively convey the practical relevance of physics for students' future professional activities.

Therefore, it is essential to effectively utilize interdisciplinary connections, explore practical applications of physical phenomena and laws, and, when appropriate, adopt a creative approach to their implementation^[6-12]. Developing students' independent working skills and competencies encourages them to approach career selection freely and consciously, thus fostering logical thinking in complex situations.

Schools possess great potential for guiding students in their professional choices, but this potential must be realized within a structured system. Increasing students' interest in physics and shaping their attitudes toward various industrial sectors are crucial. All types of lessons should be utilized efficiently and systematically to achieve this goal.

Providing polytechnic information through generalized industrial sectors rather than specific professions and developing structured lesson plans and extracurricular activities is essential. Practical knowledge should consider developmental trends in the national economy. If such trends involve transitioning toward industrial complexes, comprehensive mechanization should be prioritized.

As interests of students in grades 5–7 are not yet fully stable, their enthusiasm for certain fields may emerge suddenly and fade quickly, with one interest easily replacing another. Therefore, nurturing and stabi-

lizing students' interests is crucial. Properly organized interdisciplinary educational activities alone can stimulate students' curiosity.

To develop and sustain students' interests, lessons must be emotionally engaging, vivid, and dynamic. Educational materials should relate directly to practical applications, and students should understand the relevance of their studies to everyday life and various professional fields. Additionally, comprehending the necessity of acquiring knowledge for future career opportunities and continued education significantly enhances their motivation.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the process of career selection, students must possess broad knowledge in various subjects to correctly interpret the advice given by their parents and teachers. This is directly related to the effectiveness of interdisciplinary connections. Therefore, physics teachers should focus on ensuring that educational materials are integrated with other disciplines and provide information that highlights the prospects for industrial and technological development.

Currently, there are emerging and in-demand professions such as "Computational Physicist," "Medical Physics Engineer," "Specialist in Computational Physics," "Energy Systems Engineer," and "Data Processing Specialist in Physics." These professions require a solid foundation in interdisciplinary education, making it impossible to teach their principles without an interdisciplinary approach.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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